

EFFECT OF HEPATITIS C VIRUS ON HAEMOGLOBIN AND HAEMATOCRIT LEVELS IN ABUTH AND AKTH HAEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Persistent infection with *Hepatitis c* virus (HCV) has emerged as one of the primary causes of chronic liver disease with an estimated 170 million people infected by HCV, more than 4 times the number of people living with HIV throughout the world. Infection with *Hepatitis c* virus is common among patients undergoing haemodialysis, and haemodialysis patients are at high risk for infection with such virus. The aim of this study was to assess the seroprevalence and the effect of HCV on PCV and HB in haemodialysis patients who were consented. *Hepatitis c* virus antibody testing was carried out using CLINOTECH DIAGNOSTIC AND PHARMACEUTICAL INC. B.C. V7A 5H5, CANADA via antibody testing kit. Information about the patient demographic factors and other variables were obtained from the patients or caregivers using a designed questionnaire. A total of 88 blood samples were analysed. The overall seroprevalence rate for HCV was 7.9%. Prevalence of HCV antibody was 6.8% in males and 1.1% in females. The age group of 61-70 years has the lowest prevalence of 1.1% while those of 51-60 years had the highest value of 4.5%. In view of the prevalence rate of HCV infection in this study, it is suggested that further epidemiological studies should be conducted to establish the exact role of HCV in liver disease among haemodialysis patients in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Effect, *Hepatitis c* virus, Haemoglobin, Haematocrit, Haemodialysis, Patients.

INTRODUCTION

Despite rapid scientific progress in understanding the biology of viral illness, viral liver disease remains a common and challenging problem for physicians and their patients (Alter and Seeff, 2000). Persistent infection with *Hepatitis c* virus (HCV) has emerged as one of the primary causes of chronic liver disease with an estimated 170 million people infected by HCV, more than 4 times the number of people living with HIV throughout the world (WHO,2000). Of the typical hepatitis viruses, chronic infection with *Hepatitis c* virus remains one of the most important clinical and public health problems (El-Zayadi *et al.*, 2004). In the western world, chronic damage from *Hepatitis c* is the primary cause of the end stage liver disease requiring liver transplantation (Niederan *et al.*, 1998). The discovery of HCV in 1989 was a major breakthrough. Before that point, it was clear that a major cause of acute hepatitis after a blood transfusion was neither related to *Hepatitis A* nor to *Hepatitis B*- hence the early names for this disease, non-A, non-B hepatitis (Simmonds *et al.*, 2005).

The virus is a small (55-65nm in size), included in Group IV, enveloped, positive sense, single stranded RNA virus, the family Flaviviridae, genus Hepacivirus, and *Hepatitis c* virus type species (Simmonds *et al.*, 2005). Based on genetic differences between HCV isolates, the virus species is classified into six genotypes (1-6) with several subtypes within each genotype (represented by letters). Subtypes are further broken down into quasispecies based on their genetic diversity (Kato, 2000).

The open reading frame of the virus encodes the structural proteins core (C), enveloped (E1, E2), and the non-structural proteins (NS2, NS3, NS4a, NS4b, NS5a and NS5b) (Djebbi *et al.*, 2004).

The most efficient transmission of HCV is through large or repeated direct percutaneous exposure to blood; example transfusion or transplantation from infectious donors, injecting drugs use (William *et al.*, 2004).there is also evidence that the environment can serve as reservoir for infectious virus (Kamili *et al.*,2007). The virus has no ethnic, socio-economic, gender, age or geographic boundaries (Perz and Alter, 2006).

The virus binds to receptors on the surfaces of hepatocytes and subsequently enters the cell. Two putative HCV receptors are CD81 and human scavenger receptor class B1. However, these receptors are found throughout the body. The identification of hepatocyte-specific cofactors that determine observed HCV tropisms are currently under investigation (Sagnelli *et al.*, 2005). Prolonged survival of HCV on blood contaminated skin, cloth, and other object emphasizes the importance of fomites in nosocomial spread (Kamili *et al.*, 2007).

The main pathological features are damage to liver parenchyma which is mediated by inflammatory cytokines leading to varying degrees of hepatic fibrosis and eventually cirrhosis (Bellentani and Tribelli, 2001). Acute HCV infection is uncommonly recognised, because it is usually accompanied by mild flulike symptoms. Weight loss, fatigue, muscle or joint pain, irritability, nausea, malaise, anorexia, and jaundice have been reported in 2-26 weeks incubation period. At chronic stage of infection fatigue, depression, nausea, anorexia, abdominal discomfort, and difficulty with concentration are the predominant symptoms (Perez *et al.*, 2005). The risk factors for HCV transmission include transfusion of blood or blood products and transplantation of solid organs from infected donors, injecting drug use, unsafe therapeutic injections and occupational exposure to blood (primarily contaminated needle sticks), birth to an infected mother, and sex with an infected partner, and sex with multiple partners (Alter, 2002).

It has been well documented that dialysis patients have a higher rate of HCV infection in the 90's much of the world reported anti-HCV prevalence rates of 10-50% among haemodialysis patients with lower rates in such places as Ireland (1-7%) (Niu *et al.*,1993; Hayashi *et al.*,1994). Previously, rates in Europe were as 20-30% (Touzet *et al.*, 2000). A more recent report from Saudi Arabia showed a prevalence rate of HCV among haemodialysis patients to be 9.24% compared to 0.30% among blood donors (Qadi *et al.*, 2004).

Currently, viral culture usually in combination with immunofluorescence is the "gold standard" for laboratory diagnosis. However, it is not a rapid diagnostic test, and therefore, its clinical value is limited. Rapid antibody / or antigen detection test are now widely used in routine laboratories for the diagnosis of viral infection (Hladik *et al.*, 2006).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

The study was carried out in Ahmadu Bello Univesity Teaching Hospital (ABUTH) Zaria and Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH) Kano haemodialysis units.

ABUTH is located in Zaria on longitude 8° and latitude 9° in Kaduna state northwestern part of Nigeria.

AKTH is located in Kano on longitude 12° 37'N, 9° 29' E and latitude 9°33'S, 7°34'W in northwestern part of Nigeria respectively (Olofin *et al.*, 2008).

Sample Collection and Processing

All haemodialysis patients are included in the study. The samples were collected only from patients/care giver who has been given a written informed consent.

A dry sterile plastic syringe (5ml) with 21SWG (standard wire gauges) needle attached was used for blood sample collection. Blood was collected by applying soft tubing tourniquet to the arm of the patient to enable the veins seen and felt. The punctured site was cleansed using methylated spirit and allowed to air dried. The needle was inserted to the selected straight vein with the bevel of the needle directed upward in the line of the vein. Steadily the plunger of the syringe was withdrawn until 5ml of blood is obtained. The tourniquet was released and the needle was removed from the punctured vein. Pressure was applied to the punctured site to secure homeostasis. The needle was removed from the syringe and the blood was transferred to a clean anticoagulant specimen bottle (Ethelyne diamine tetracetic acid- EDTA), mixed and labelled properly. The used syringes and needles were disposed appropriately.

HB and PCV Determination

This was carried out immediately after sample collection as described by Cheesbrough (2000).

HCV Antibody Detection

This was carried out using commercially prepared antibody testing kit based on the manufacturer's instructions (CLINTOCH DIAGNOSTIC Ltd, USA).

Data Analysis

Data obtained from the study was analysed using correlation and the chi-square test of association with a p-value of 0.05 as statistically significant and the prevalent rate of the infection was analysed as percentage. These were achieved using computerized statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

A total of 88 blood samples from haemodialysis patients were tested for the presence of HCV antibody. Among the samples tested, seven (7.9%) were seropositive.

Table 1 shows the seroprevalence of HCV antibody among the studied population with respect to age. Of the total samples tested, 7(8 %) were age group 10-20 years, 14(15.9%) were aged 21-30 years, 22(25%) were aged 31-40 years, 19(22%) were aged 41-50 years, 14(16) were aged 51-60 years, 7(8%) were aged 61-70 years, 4(6%) were aged 71-80 years, while 1(1.1%) were aged 81-90 years. The seroprevalence was highest (4.5%) in age group 51-60 years and lowest in age group 61-70 years (1.1%). The result shows increased seropositivity with age. $R= 0.302$, $P = 0.004$.

Among the 88 haemodialysis patients tested, 60(68%) were male and 28(32%) were females. This shows that there was male predominance over females, which was not statistically significant ($X^2 = 0.299$, $P= 0.288$). As seen in Table 2.

Of the total 88 haemodialysis patients, 1 (1.1%) had PCV within 16-20%, 3(3.4%) had PCV within 21-30 and 3(3.4%) had PCV within 31-40%. Association has not been found between PCV and HCV seropositivity (Correlation co-efficient ' r '=0.150, P value=0.162) Table 3.

Among the patients tested, 3 (3.4%) had Haemoglobin (Hb) within 1-5 g/dl but none of them was seropositive, 77 (87.5%) had Hb within 6-10 g/dl and 4(4.5%) were seropositive, 8(9%) had Hb of within 11-15 g/dl and 3(3.4%) were found to be seropositive. Although it was found not to be significant ($r = 0.126$, P value = 0.244) Table 4.

Table 5 shows that out of the total patients tested, 78(88.6%) within 1-100 has (3.4%) of the total 7.9% seropositivity. 3(3.4%) had dialysis within 101-200, although there was no seropositive sample found among them, 5(5.7%) had dialysis within 201-300 and 2.3% of the total 7.9% seropositivity was found in these group. 1 (1.1%) of the patients tested had dialysis within 301- 400 and 501-600 each respectively. The result shows statistical association between frequency of dialysis and HCV seropositivity ($r= 0.430$, P value 0.000).

Among the total population tested, 52 (59.1%) had history of blood transfusion and 36(41%) had no history of blood transfusion. 3(3.4%) seropositivity was found in those with history of blood transfusion out of the total 7.9% seroprevalence while 4.5% seropositivity was found in those without history of blood transfusion. The seropositivity was found to be more in those without history of blood transfusion, although it was not statistically significant ($r= 0.043$, $P= 0.690$) Table 6.

Table 1: Distribution of HCV Antibody by Age.

Age (years)	Number tested	Number Seropositive	% Seropositive per each Age Group	% Seropositive for Overall Total
10-20	7	0	0	0
21-30	14	0	0	0
31-40	22	0	0	0
41-50	19	0	0	0
51-60	14	4	28.6	4.5
61-70	7	1	14.3	1.1
71-80	4	2	50	2.27
81-90	1	0	0	0
Total	88	7		7.9

$r = 0.302, P = 0.004$

Table 2: Distribution of HCV Antibody by Sex

Sex	Number of patients tested	Number Seropositive	% Seropositive
Male	60	6	6.8
Female	28	1	1.1
Total	88	7	7.9

$X^2 = 0.299, P = 0.288$

Table 3: PCV Distribution of HCV Antibody

PCV (%)	Number tested	Number seropositive	% Seropositive
10-15	4	0	0
16-20	18	1	1.1
21-30	57	3	3.4
31-40	9	3	3.4
Total	88	7	7.9

Correlation co-efficient 'r' = 0.150, P value = 0.162

Table 4: Hb (g/dl) and Distribution of HCV Antibody

Hb (g/dl)	Number tested	Number seropositive	% Seropositive
1-5	3	0	0
6-10	77	4	4.5
11-15	8	3	3.4
Total	88	7	7.9

$r = 0.126, P \text{ value} = 0.244$

Table 5: Frequency of Dialysis and the HCV Antibody

Frequency of Dialysis	Number tested	Number seropositive	% Seropositive
1-100	78	3	3.4
101-200	3	0	0
201-300	5	2	2.3
301-400	1	1	1.1
401-500	0	0	0
501-600	1	1	1.1
Total	88	7	7.9

$r = 0.430, P \text{ value} = 0.000$

Table 6: Blood Transfusion and Distribution of HCV Antibody

Blood Transfusion	Number tested	Number Seropositive	% Seropositive
Yes	52	3	3.4
No	36	4	4.5
Total	88	7	7.9

$r = 0.043, P = 0.690$

DISCUSSION

Despite rapid scientific progress in understanding the biology of viral illness, viral liver disease remains a common and challenging problem for physicians and their patients (Alter and Seeff, 2000). Persistent infection with *Hepatitis c* virus (HCV) has emerged as one of the primary causes of chronic liver disease with an estimated 170 million people infected by HCV, more than 4 times the number of people living with HIV throughout the world (WHO,2000). Of the typical hepatitis viruses, chronic infection with *Hepatitis c* virus remains one of the most important clinical and public health problems (El-Zayadi *et al.*, 2004).

The present study found 7(7.9%) of the subject to be seropositive for HCV antibody. This is slightly above the finding of Nwokede *et al* (2007) who demonstrated 6.2% prevalence in Kano haemodialysis patients, Mendez-Sanchez *et al* (2004) who reported 6.7% prevalence in Mexican dialysis patients and Dede *et al* (2007) who demonstrated 7% prevalence in Turkey haemodialysis patients. While it contrast the finding of Kalantan-Zadeh *et al* (2007) who reported 12% prevalence in USA dialysis patients, Chen *et al* (2008) who demonstrated 20.6% prevalence in Taiwan dialysis patients, Al-Jamal *et al* (2009) who reported 28% prevalence in Jodanian dialysis patients, Al-saran *et al* (2009) who reported 33% prevalence in Saudi Arabia dialysis patients, Barril *et al* (2008) who demonstrated 45% prevalence in Spain dialysis patients and Sabry *et al* (2007) who reported 70.7% prevalence in Egyptian haemodialysis patients.

The study also reveals an increase in seropositivity with age. This finding conforms to those of Sabry *et al* (2007) and Barril *et al* (2008) who reported increase seropositivity with age. This could be due to the fact that people of older age are more susceptible to infectious micro-organism.

In assessing the sex distribution of HCV antibody seropositivity was observed to be higher in male (6.8%) than in female (1.1%).This could be as a result of behavioural exposure to the risk factor which is more in males than females. Although the result was not statistically significant (P= 0.288).

In assessing the HCV seropositivity in respect to PCV and Hb values it has been observed that HCV has no effect on PCV and Hb. This conforms to the finding of Sabry *et al* (2007) who has reported to have found no effect of HCV infection on PCV and Hb values. This is in contrast with the finding of Sahin *et al* (2003) and Chen *et al* (2008) who reported an increase PCV and Hb in HCV positive haemodialysis patients in their studies. The lack of consistency between the present study and that of Sahin *et al* (2003) and Chen *et al* (2008) results could be explained by: the haemodialysis duration was longer in most patients in the present study compared to the very short (12.5 ± 9 months) one in the HCV-negative patients of Sahin's study and this can be partially explain their lower haemoglobin level.

This study showed that seropositivity is higher in those with high frequency of dialysis. This conforms to the finding of with the finding of Al-Jamal *et al* (2009). This could be due to the fact that dialysis duration has been found to be one of the risk factor of acquiring HCV infection.

The present study shows that there is no association between HCV infection and blood transfusion. This is in contrast with the finding of Zoulin (1999), Pol *et al* (2002) and Dede *et al* (2007) that has incriminated blood transfusion as one of the risk factor for HCV infection.

CONCLUSION

The present study has revealed the importance of HCV as an etiologic agent of Liver disease in haemodialysis patients. The study emphasizes the need to rapidly diagnose viral infections for clinical management of infected dialysis patients. It also provide epidemiological data that may be useful in control effort and vaccine trials, mostly in developing countries where less information regarding viral infection in haemodialysis patients is available.

RECOMMENDATION

In view of the prevalence rate of *Hepatitis c* virus seropositivity in this study, it is recommended that attention should be given to this virus for proper management of patients with liver disease especially in those with symptoms of end stage kidney malfunction.

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